

dormancy of about 12 wk. It is moderately resistant to sheath blight, brown spot, and stem borer.

The 1984 Annual Rice Workshop

(AICRIP) recommended NC492 as a promising variety for semideep water situations in West Bengal, Bihar, Orissa, and Andhra Pradesh. It has been

recommended for minikit demonstration trials in farmers fields for 2 yr and is in the prerelease stage in West Bengal. *ℓ*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Character association in upland rice cultivars of India

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Ninety-eight local rice cultivars grown in a randomized block design with three replications in July 1983 were assessed

for the association among 11 traits at the genotypic (r_g) and phenotypic (r_p) levels (see table).

In general, genotypic associations were higher than phenotypic, but values of both were either positive or negative. This indicates that r_p is slightly reduced by environmental effects. At both the r_g and r_p levels, yield per plant was positive and significantly associated with days to flowering, leaf angle, leaf length, plant height, panicle length, sheath length,

tillers per plant, and grains per panicle. Yield per plant was associated with test weight only at the r_g level. Tillers per plant and test weight directly contributed to yield. Other auxiliary traits that showed positive association with yield were also positively associated among themselves. Any one of these traits could be utilized as selection criteria for yield improvement in upland rice. *ℓ*

Genotypic (G) and phenotypic (P) associations among 11 traits of upland rices.^a

Trait		Culm angle	Leaf angle	Leaf length	Plant height	Panicle length	Sheath length	Tillers/plant	Grains/panicle	Test weight	Grain yield/plant
Days to flowering	G	-0.08	0.45**	0.52**	0.53**	0.58**	0.40**	0.05	0.49**	-0.06	0.31**
	P	-0.08	0.41**	0.37**	0.50**	0.48**	0.26**	0.03	0.41**	-0.07	0.20*
Culm angle	G		0.17	0.14	-0.21*	-0.25**	0.11	-0.10	-0.13	0.20*	-0.08
	P		0.17	0.08	-0.17	-0.17	0.05	0.01	-0.05	0.16	0.01
Leaf angle	G			0.42**	0.55**	0.39**	0.45**	0.15	0.55**	0.06	0.36**
	P			0.30**	0.49**	0.32**	0.32**	0.06**	0.43**	0.06	0.20*
Leaf length	G				0.75**	0.67**	0.89**	-0.29**	0.51**	0.19	0.54**
	P				0.58**	0.58**	0.65**	-0.10	0.36**	0.14	0.31**
Plant height	G					0.73**	0.68**	-0.17	0.57**	0.01	0.63**
	P					0.67**	0.52**	-0.07	0.47**	0.10	0.43**
Panicle length	G						0.57**	-0.16	0.51**	-0.10	0.49**
	P						0.45**	-0.05	0.54**	0.20	0.34**
Sheath length	G							-0.24*	0.53**	0.09	0.43**
	P							-0.26	0.37**	0.06	0.27**
Tillers/plant	G								-0.31**	-0.26**	0.20*
	P								0.22*	-0.19*	0.29**
Grains/panicle	G									0.43**	0.26**
	P									-0.37**	0.36**
Test weight	G										0.27**
	P										0.09

^aSignificant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Hot water treatment of rice seed for international shipment

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Hot water treatment to control several seedborne pathogens of rice is a widely used quarantine practice in the international exchange of germplasm. One limitation to its use is potentially

deleterious effects on germination and seedling vigor. The possibility that genotypes may differ substantially in sensitivity to hot water treatment poses serious complications in the interpretation of international testing data.

The effect of different hot water treatments and different posttreatment storage conditions on the seed quality of

four rice cultivars was studied. The cultivars were japonica and indica ecotypes to represent sensitive and resistant responses to hot water treatment. Temperature limits and exposure periods tested encompassed the range of treatment conditions recommended for rice by ASEAN quarantine officials.

Seed quality changes were evaluated